

D5.5 (M12)- Report of “Framework for achieving import of sensitive data obtained from external sources and deployed infrastructure for ELIXIR BioContainers repository in secure compute environments”

(an ELIXIR Norway ELIXIR₃ deliverable)

Project name: ELIXIR₃ - strengthening the Norwegian Node of ELIXIR

Project duration: 2022-04-01 - 2026-03-31 (48 months)

Funder: The Research Council of Norway

Project number: [322392](#)

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Publication date: 2024-02-23

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10697471](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10697471)

Keywords: research infrastructure, e-infrastructure, secure compute environment, biocontainers, trusted research environments.

Context

This report details the progress of Deliverable 5.5 "Framework for achieving import of sensitive data obtained from external sources and deployed infrastructure for ELIXIR BioContainers repository in secure compute environments", aimed at the import and integration of non-sensitive data sourced externally and the deployment of pre-built BioContainers into secure computing environments commonly known as Trusted Research Environment (TREs). The report outlines the current status, the challenges tackled, and the objectives defined for deploying a robust and efficient infrastructure.

Through the integration of BioContainers, a collection of containerised, open-source bioinformatics software packages, this deliverable further broadens the range of computational resources accessible to researchers, provided within a secure environment.

Background Information:

The integration of the CernVM File System (CVMFS)¹ into TREs is identified as a crucial step toward streamlining the usage of large-scale reference data and software tools required for bioinformatics research. CVMFS is a distributed file system designed to deliver read-only data efficiently to end-users. It operates in user space as a FUSE module, adhering to POSIX

¹ <https://cvmfs.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

standards. Its current utilisation in projects such as Galaxy²; CVMFS demonstrates its capability to disseminate bioinformatics data resources, including reference genomes and singularity based BioContainers³, effectively.

Current challenges:

Accessing and setting up standardised bioinformatics tools within Trusted Research Environments (TREs) often requires considerable computational expertise from research teams, as well as occasional support and customisation from TREs personnel to fit the project's unique requirements. . At the same time, TREs maintain rigorous security protocols, which can create certain constraints on data import from external resources. Even with initiatives in place to streamline the import of non-sensitive data, achieving this while maintaining the high standards of security continues to be a challenge.

Delivery

- Evaluation of infrastructure security requirements for TREs, currently for the Services for sensitive data at the University of Oslo (TSD)⁴.
- Evaluation of compute, network and storage requirements.
- Drafting of a risk and vulnerability analysis and project documentation.
- Ongoing: Establish and test infrastructure within TSD.

Outcomes

The primary beneficiaries of enhanced Trusted Research Environments (TREs) such as TSD, SAFE⁵, and HUNT Cloud⁶ are the researchers utilising these platforms. Essentially, these improvements will render the TREs more effective and appealing platforms for secure and collaborative research endeavours. The introduction of a framework for non-sensitive data and tools integration will also pave the way for collaboration between TREs which have so far mostly operated independently.

Upon successfully implementing and testing the new framework and infrastructure within TSD, it will translate across other TREs. Thus, this framework will establish a precedent and benchmark within other TREs.

² <https://usegalaxy.eu/>

³ <https://biocontainers.pro/>

⁴ <https://www.uio.no/english/services/it/research/sensitive-data/>

⁵ <https://www.uib.no/safe>

⁶ <https://www.ntnu.edu/mh/huntcloud>